

Studies on Electrodeposition of Cobalt in Ammonical Acetate Bath

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Manuscript received 17 December 1993, revised 23 November 1994, accepted 1 February 1995

A new alkaline bath for deposition of cobalt has been made from cobalt hydroxide dissolved in solution of ammonium acetate. Various parameters such as influence of concentrations of cobalt ions and ammonium acetate, pH, current density and temperature are reported. The proposed bath lowers the overall cost of electrodeposition and provides desired level of quality of deposits. The deposits are adherent and stable to prolonged atmospheric exposure.

Rigorous efforts have been made for electrodeposition of cobalt in the recent years. Several baths for plating cobalt and its alloys have been investigated¹. However for many baths, although the deposits obtained are mirror-bright, they get cracked on prolonged exposure to air.

In the present work, a new type of bath is proposed for electrodeposition of cobalt, i.e. dilute ammoniacal acetate bath, which lowers the overall cost of deposition and provides bright adherent deposits.

Results and Discussion

Influence of concentration of cobalt sulphate : Various concentrations (1–7%) were tried. Higher concentrations were not possible because of the restricted solubility of cobalt hydroxide in ammonium acetate. At low (1 and 2%) as well as at high (6–7%) concentrations of cobalt sulphate, the deposits were not satisfactory. They were black, dull and cloudy, while those obtained at moderate concentrations (3–4%) were quite satisfactory. It was observed that %CCE increased with increase in concentration of cobalt sulphate initially, and remained constant at higher concentrations (above 4%). At higher concentrations there was no appreciable decrease in the concentration of metal ions during electrolysis, hence %CCE remained constant.

Influence of concentration of ammonium acetate : Ammonium acetate was used as complexing agent, the concentration of which was varied from 12 to 42% of the bath solution. At lower concentration of ammonium acetate (12%), the bath solution was turbid, indicating that the quantity of the acetate was insufficient to cause dissolution of the precipitate of cobalt hydroxide and hence formation of complex could not take place. This was further confirmed by the fact that no deposit was obtained at this concentration of ammonium acetate. When the concentration of ammonium acetate was further increased to 18%,

the turbidity disappeared and the bath solution became clear, indicating formation of the complex. The deposit obtained at this concentration was most satisfactory. With increase in the concentration of the acetate, nature of the deposits and %CCE were found to be affected. They were dull, black and nonuniform, while %CCE decreased by 73%. This marked decrease may be attributed to evolution of ammonia gas at the cathode, due to high concentration of ammonium acetate as well as possible adsorption of negatively charged ligand, viz. $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3]^-$ and/or $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_4]^{2-}$ on the surface of the cathode, resulting in an increase in cathode polarisation and hence decrease in %CCE². This process caused the blackening of the deposits. The optimum condition selected for concentration of ammonium acetate was taken as 18% of the bath solution.

Influence of pH : The pH of the bath solution was varied from 5.5 to 8.0. It was observed that in the acidic medium (pH 5.5–6.7) the magnitude of %CCE was almost constant, while after pH 7 it increased substantially and later (beyond pH 8) remained constant. The nature of the deposits changed from bright to dull white. The increase in %CCE can be attributed to the increase in concentration of NH_4^+ ions in the bath (hence near cathode). The worsening appearance of the deposits at higher pH can be explained on the basis of the effects of decrease in polarisation. The decrease in polarisation may be due to the adsorbed complex anions on the cathode, due to increase in pH. The optimum condition selected for pH was 6.7, for further work.

Influence of current density (C.D.) : The study was carried out at pH 6.7. The results indicate that %CCE depends on two opposing factors, when C.D. is the variable. The availability of metal ions at cathode favours the increase in %CCE, while the distribution of current at higher C.D. into deposition of the metal as well as evolution of hydrogen gas at the cathode decreases %CCE. Hence %CCE under-

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goes the maximum, when studied as a function of C.D. and optimum condition was at 0.5 A dm^{-2} .

Influence of temperature : At low temperature (10°) the deposit was nonadherent, and showed treeing effect. The effect decreased with the increase in temperature. This might be due to the increase in the mobility of metal ions at the higher temperature, so that a rapid replenishing of cathode film could take place, resulting in disappearance of treeing. With increase in temperature, initially %CCE increased gradually followed by a marked decrease at higher temperatures. It is reasoned that when temperature is increased upto 30° , the mobility of ions is increased thus increasing rate of diffusion of metal ions near the cathode, resulting in an increase in %CCE, while at higher temperatures evolution of hydrogen gas (due to higher rate constants) is the factor causing the decrease in %CCE.

Conclusion : The optimum conditions derived experimentally for various parameters are as follows : composition of bath-4% cobalt sulphate and 18% ammonium acetate; pH, 6.7; current density, 0.5 A dm^{-2} ; temperature, 30° ; interelectrode distance, 2 cm; duration of electrolysis, 20 min.

The proposed bath lowers the overall cost of electrodeposition, the bath being dilute. It also gives a shining uniform fine grad and adherent deposits. It overcomes the problem of extraction of cobalt from the waste liquors. Further, electrodeposition of cobalt lowers the pollution due to the effluents, to the minimum. The bath provides well adherent stable deposits even after a prolonged ex-

posure to the atmosphere, thus removing the drawback of the conventional baths.

Experimental

The bath solution was prepared by slowly adding requisite quantity of 25% ammonia solution to a desired quantity of 30% freshly prepared cobalt sulphate solution till the precipitation of cobalt in the form of cobalt hydroxide was complete. The precipitate obtained was in the form of thick paste and as such no solution was left behind. The paste was then dissolved completely by adding requisite quantity of 60% ammonium acetate, to obtain a clear solution.

Different bath solutions were prepared by taking different quantities of cobalt sulphate (1-7%). Here although complex was formed, every time it indirectly measured the effect of concentration of cobalt sulphate.

A copper coulometer³ was used to measure the quantity of electricity passing through the bath and hence to find out percent cathode current efficiency (CCE) of the process.

References

1. F. R. MORRAL, *Plating*, 1967, **55**, 693; K. FOVERTTSIN, *Electrokhimya*, 1986, **22**, 9; A. B. MARKEVICIUS, *Electrokhimya*, 1976; MIKUE-NIST R. MAULEUSRENCE, *Met. Electrokhimya Lit S. S. R.* 1978, E. CHEN. United States Department of Army S. S. 41, 1978, pp. 111, 760.
2. C. A. SANVELY, *Proc. Am. Electroplat. Soc.*, 1961, **47**, 138; H. J. READ, "Hydrogen Embrittlement in Metal Finishing", Reihold, New York, 1971; T. RADHAKRISHNAN and L. SHREIR, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1966, **11**, 1007; S. GLASSTONE *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2414.
3. OTEL, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1993, **17**, 553.

